

Complex Probabilities in Free Particle Quantum Mechanics

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Classical probability follows a set of rules. Probabilities are represented by real positive numbers between 0 and 1 which represent states which may be measured at different times without changing their values. For example, when one tosses a die or coin, one may measure the outcome. If one measures it at t_1 and no further toss occurs, then one may measure it again at $t_2 > t_1$ and obtain the same result. Thus, we argue that stating that a particle moving with constant speed has a probability in Δx proportional to Δt does not conform to classical probability because a measurement at t_2 does not yield the same result as at t_1 . We note that in classical probability, probabilities sum to 1 even though they represent events that occur at different times. Thus, probability is a real valued quantity that is conserved. Furthermore, one has AND and OR (i.e. multiply and add) rules.

In a set of previous notes (1), we tried to introduce a different kind of probability based largely on conservation of energy and momentum in Newtonian mechanics. We argued that for a given initial set of energies and momenta (e_1, e_2) (p_1, p_2) vector in a two-body elastic scattering event, there is equal product probability for any (e_i, e_j) (p_i, p_j) vectors set if conservation of energy and momentum are maintained. We argued in (1) that this leads to a complex probability $\exp(-iEt + i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ which is Lorentz invariant. The unit modulus means that all free particles carry the same real value coefficient 1 as one is creating a probability which is concerned only with conservation. We also noted in (1) that $\exp(i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ is time reversal invariant.

Given our argument that $P(x)$ proportional to Δt is not a classical probability due to the measurement problem, we ask how one may convert a $P_1(p, x)$ (like $\exp(ipx)$) into a classical probability. $\exp(ipx)$ is created using the notion of an AND product probability and so to satisfy the different time measurement condition of a classical probability, one must convert $\exp(ipx)$ into a particle that does not move. This is done by the AND process $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx) = P_1(p, x)P_1(-p, x)$. Thus, $\exp(ipx)$ should satisfy AND (multiply) and OR (add) rules. $\exp(ipx)$, however, does not seem to represent a quantity as classical probabilities do. Thus, in the case of an OR (add) scenario, one may wonder what one is really adding. It is still, however, unclear as to what quantity $\exp(ipx)$ represents. In order to illuminate this issue, we try to analyze the case of one dimensional reflection-refraction at an n_1 - n_2 (index of refraction) junction.

Classical Probability

Classical probability is based on real positive numbers between 0 and 1 which sum to 1. In AND situations, probabilities multiply and in OR, they sum. Thus, probability is like a quantity which is conserved, with each probability representing a different outcome or state which does not change in time until another outcome occurs. We suggest that this latter property is important. It implies that writing $P_1(x)$ proportional to Δt for a particle moving with constant speed is not a classical probability. This has consequences because one may consider a classical Newtonian elastic two body collision and try to introduce probability in the following way. For any given (e_1, e_2) and (p_1, p_2) vectors (energy and momentum), one may argue that

any (e_i, e_j) (p_i, p_j) vectors set may occur with the same product (AND) probability as long as energy and momentum are conserved. In (1), we showed that this leads to a probability of:

$$\exp(-iEt + i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r}) \quad ((1))$$

((1)) is certainly not a real positive number between 0 and 1. Nor does $\exp(i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{x})$ seem to represent a physical quantity which is distributed among different possible states which exist at different times. $\exp(i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{x})$ is dynamic in that it depends on both \mathbf{p} and the sign of \mathbf{p} . We have argued that for a moving object one cannot define a classical probability as being proportional to Δt . Thus, it seems that $\exp(ipx)$ maps or is associated with a classical probability by using an AND (multiply) condition:

$$P(x) = 1 = P_1(p, x)P_1(-p, x) = \exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx) \quad ((2)) \text{ for } L=1=\text{arbitrary length}$$

As a result, any \mathbf{p} value maps into the same $P(x)=1$ as the classical probability $P(x)$ represents a stationary particle such that its position may be measured at t_1 and $t_2 > t_1$. Physical interactions, usually described by Newtonian mechanics, however, are dynamic. For classical physics, a quantity of probability is conserved, but for conservation of momentum, it is momentum that is conserved. We argued that for classical probability, a stationary object must be considered for x measurements. The dynamic probability $\exp(ipx)$ is concerned with \mathbf{p} conservation not x , but in (1) we showed that one must use $\exp(i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{x})$ and so x appears and this probability must also somehow be linked to position. One, however, does not have a stationary object and so cannot call $\exp(ipx)$ a classical probability. Given, however, that it is linked to x and is overall some kind of probability, it should map to a stationary object. In other words, the key idea seems to be that one transforms from a probability linked to conservation of momentum $\exp(ipx)$ to one associated with the position of a stationary object in space $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx)$. Later, we show that this approach may be generalized as $\exp(ipx)$ may carry a weight if there is more than one particle. Given that this is a dynamic probability, we will argue for a weight linked to flux rather than particle number.

Thus, $\exp(ipx)$ is not a classical probability, but satisfies AND and presumably OR conditions, and acts as a probability in these scenarios. In order to obtain a classical probability, one must consider an AND situation which is equivalent to

$$P_1^*(p, x)P_1(p, x) \quad ((3)) \text{ in the example of } ((2))$$

This begs the question: What weight does $\exp(ipx)$ physically represent? How is it possible that it is linked to a usual classical probability? To try to answer these questions, we consider the case of 1-D reflection-refraction.

One Dimensional Reflection Refraction

One dimensional reflection-refraction at an n_1 - n_2 index of refraction junction leads to a classical probability statement:

$$1 = \text{Probability}(\text{reflect}) + \text{Probability}(\text{refract}) \quad ((3))$$

The probabilities are real positive numbers between 0 and 1 and represent events which occur at different times. The problem is that Newtonian mechanics does not allow one to calculate these probabilities even though they may be measured. This might suggest that there is some unknown information about the interaction which occurs. Measurement, however, may show that the energy of the incident, reflected and refracted photons are the same. In Newtonian mechanics, one may describe a particle through $x(t)$ or through an energy conservation equation. One may examine a process in terms of energy and 1-D reflection-refraction does not involve any energy change. Any forces seem to be internal as in a Newtonian particle moving in a circle. This seems to imply that the probabilities of ((3)) are built-in, but it is not clear how to obtain them.

We first note that even though classical probability represents a conserved quantity, one may write ((3)) as:

$$AA/c_1 - BB/c_1 = CC/c_2 \quad ((4))$$

Here c_1 and c_2 are the speeds of light in media n_1 and n_2 and $E=pc$. AA , BB and CC are the fluxes of the incident, reflected and refracted probabilities. What has been done in ((4)) is to write the classical probability expression in terms of dynamic quantities. This is allowable and one may note that physically, the problem is dynamic. We also note that some kind of interaction occurs as a photon moves from n_1 to n_2 even if E does not change. This interaction should respect conservation of momentum and so we argue that it should somehow be associated with

$$\exp(ipx) \quad ((5))$$

which we postulated above. $\exp(ipx)$, however, does not appear in ((4)), but given the idea of

$$1 = \exp(ipx) \exp(-ipx) \quad ((6))$$

one might inquire whether $\exp(ipx)$ s may be used to obtain ((4)) just as $\exp(ipx)$ is used in ((6)) to obtain 1.

Mathematically, this question may be answered immediately because ((4)) may be written as:

$$1/c_1 (A-B)(A+B) = CC/c_2 c_2 \quad 1/c = p/E \quad \text{so} \quad p(A-B)(A+B) = p^2(C) \quad ((7))$$

((7)) is now equivalent to a balance of a kind of pressure in space. Thus, it is pressure now, albeit a mathematical scenario because different times are mixed, and not the probability of an event which appears in the classical probability expression.

This implies:

$$A \exp(ipx) + B \exp(-ipx) = C \exp(ip^2x) \text{ at } x=0 \text{ and } pA \exp(ipx) - pB \exp(-ipx) = C p^2 \exp(ip^2x) \text{ at } x=0 \quad ((8))$$

In other words, there is continuity of $\exp(ipx)$ and its derivative d/dx .

This allows one to solve the problem for B and C in terms of A. One sees that in this approach A is the square root of flux, a dynamical quantity. $\exp(ipx)$ is carrying the weight of p, but is also a quantity (complex and function of x) which is conserved in x (i.e. at $x=0$) if one does not consider time. $\exp(ipx)$ is time reversal invariant suggesting that it is not linked to time, as argued in (1), but dynamics are usually linked to time. Here, they are linked to conservation of momentum. Given that there are dynamics and interactions underlying a classical probability ((4)) and that this dynamical probability may be “natural”, i.e. not arise from some specific stochasticity of the interaction other than conservation of momentum (i.e. $\exp(ipx)$), then ((8)) seems to a valid scenario which needs to be tested experimentally (as has been done).

Even though $\exp(ipx)$ does not seem to be a weight, it is one as well as weighting dynamical quantities such as p and even $p^2/2m$. In particular, one might write:

$$\text{Sum over } p \frac{p^2}{2m} \exp(ipx) / (\text{Sum over } j \exp(ipx) + V(x)) = E \quad ((9))$$

((9)) is the time-independent Schrodinger equation. Thus, $\exp(ipx)$ is very much a weight even though it is not the usual “quantity” of classical probability. It enforces conservation of momentum in interactions as well as being probabilistic (and $\exp(-iEt + ip \cdot r)$ is Lorentz invariant). Finally, it may be linked to classical probability statements such as ((4)), by finding ways to remove the $\exp(ipx)$ form. In the usual case, $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p a(p) \exp(ipx)$, this is done through $W^*(x)W(x)$.

Thus, the point we wish to make is that one may a priori postulate the form $\exp(ipx)$, but then one may see it appear naturally in ((4)) as a way of solving the problem with no other dynamical probabilistic condition other than:

$$\exp(ip_1x) \exp(ip_2x) = \exp(i(p_1+p_2)x) \quad ((10))$$

Conclusion

In conclusion, we consider various properties of a classical probability, We then consider a probability which might arise in Newtonian 2-body elastic scattering such that for an initial (e_1, e_2) (p_1, p_2) any set (e_i, e_j) (p_i, p_j) which conserves energy and momentum has the same product probability. This seems like a usual AND probabilistic statement, but in (1) we show that this leads to the nonclassical probability $\exp(-iEt + ip \cdot r)$. This involves dynamics and so it is

appropriate that it is Lorentz invariant. $\exp(-i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ is also time reversal invariant, suggesting that it is not linked to the flow of time. Nevertheless, it is difficult to imagine what probabilistic quantity $\exp(ipx)$ represents.

As a result, we consider a dynamical probabilistic problem, namely reflection-refraction at an n_1 - n_2 index of refraction junction. This has the usual classical probabilistic statement $1 = \text{Probability}(\text{reflect}) + \text{Probability}(\text{refract})$. This may be written in terms of dynamical variables as:

$$AAp - BBp = CCp^2 \quad ((11))$$

Here AA, BB and CC are fluxes of the incident, reflected and refracted photon and we have used $E=pc$ with E remaining constant. One may see then that ((11)) may be immediately linked to the continuity of an OR scenario using $\exp(ipx)$ and its first derivative, i.e.

$$A\exp(ipx) + B\exp(-ipx) = C\exp(ip_2x) \text{ and } A\exp(ipx) - pB\exp(-ipx) = C\exp(ip_2x) \text{ at } x=0.$$

As a result, $\exp(ipx)$ emerges as a quantity in its own right which is continuous at $x=0$ as well as a weight for p (and other functions) which is also continuous at $x=0$. Even given a classical probabilistic equation ((11)) representing a clearly time-dependent dynamic problem, there is an underlying interaction based probability $\exp(ipx)$ which gives rise to ((11)). Even though $\exp(ipx)$ does not appear to be a usual probability weight because it is complex, it acts as one by itself and as the factor of functions of p . It is time reversal invariant, so there is no time flow and one may consider OR situations which mix events of different times. In such a case, the quantity being conserved is $AAp - BBp$ and CCp^2 which is a kind of pressure at $x=0$, but in a probabilistic sense (i.e. a steady stream sense). Thus $\exp(ipx)$ is the driver of steady state classical probability which ensures probabilistic conservation of momentum $\exp(ip_1x)\exp(ip_2x) = \exp(ip_3x)\exp(ip_4x) = \exp(iPx)$ with $p_1+p_2=p_3+p_4 = P$.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. The Significance of Time Reversal Invariance of the Quantum Free $\exp(i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ (preprint, zenodo, 2025)